

IMPORTANCE OF AI IN EDUCATION

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As illustrated by Henry Ford in the analogy, innovation does not mean working that the society should work only with what has been the norm, such as finding ways of making horses faster. Sometimes, it is necessary to search beyond the norm, develop new ways of doing things. Instead of making horses faster, build the automobile, which will be faster than the horse and take a person from Point A to Point B faster. These principles and approaches have driven the rapid developments in technology experienced over the years, particularly in the education sector. The introduction, advancements, and proliferation of technology, more particularly, artificial intelligence, has made it easier for instructors to dispense their duties more effectively and efficiently.

Prior to the introduction of computers and other related technologies, instructors and students, engaged in instructions and learning mechanically, or through the pure application of natural human effort. With the introduction of microcomputers, and by extension, personal computers in the 1970s, which according to Flamm, provided more computing power and marked an important transition to electronic computers for the mass market¹. In agreement, CampbellKelly opined that with developments of the electronic computers more particularly, and the availability of the same for different entities across different sectors of the economy, was precipitated by the developments of personal computers in the 1970s². Personal computers development made it possible for individuals and other non-governmental entities to own and use computers for different reasons. These transitions harbingered the proliferation of computers in different sectors of the economy and society.

Computer and information communication technologies have over the years continued to evolve, leading to the development of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence, according to Coppin, is the ability of machines to adapt to new situations, deal with emerging situations, solve problems, answer questions, device plans, and perform various other functions that require some level of intelligence typically evident in human beings. In another definition, Whitby defined artificial intelligence as the study of intelligence behavior in human beings, animals, and machines and endeavoring to engineer such behavior into an artifact, such as computers and computer-related technologies. Drawing from these definitions, it is evident that artificial intelligence is the culmination of computers, computer-related technologies, machines, and information communication technology innovations and developments, giving computers the ability to perform near or human-like functions. In line with the adoption and use of new technologies in education, artificial intelligence has also been extensively leveraged in the education sector³.

¹ K. Flamm, *Creating the Computer: Government, Industry, and High Technology*. Washington, DC, USA: Brookings Institution Press, 2018.

² M. Campbell-Kelly, *Computer, Student Economy Edition: A History of the Information Machine*. Evanston, IL, USA: Routledge, 2018.

³ B. Coppin, *Artificial Intelligence Illuminated*. Boston, MA, USA: Jones and Bartlett, 2014.

The mention of artificial intelligence brings to mind a supercomputer, a computer with immense processing capabilities, including adaptive behavior, such as inclusion of sensors, and other capabilities, that enable it to have human-like cognition and functional abilities, and indeed, which improve the supercomputers interaction with human beings. Indeed, different motion pictures have been made to showcase the abilities of AI, such as in smart buildings, such as the ability to manage air quality in a building, temperatures, and or playing music depending on the sensed mood of the occupants of the space. Within the education sector, there has been increased application of artificial intelligence, going over and above the conventional understanding of AI as a supercomputer to include embedded computer systems. For example, embedded into robots, AI, or computers and supporting equipment enable the creation of robots that improve the learning experience of the student, from the most basic unit of education, early childhood education. Indeed, Timms posited that cobots or the application of robots, working together with teachers or colleague robots (cobots) are being applied to teach children routine tasks, including spelling and pronunciation and adjusting to the students' abilities. Artificial intelligence in education, according to Chassignol et al. has been incorporated into administration, instruction or teaching, and learning. These areas, which Chassignol et al. identify as the framework for analyzing and understanding artificial intelligence in education, will form the scope of this study⁴.

Machine learning, learning analytics, and data mining are closely related technologies for education. At present, two communities have evolved based on learning analytics and educational data mining. They overlap in objectives and techniques and benefit from a variety of disciplines, including machine learning, data mining, psychometrics of statistics, and data modelling. The field of learning analytics is more focused on learning content management systems and large-scale test results. Data mining originates from the community of intelligent tutoring systems, work on very small scale cognition⁵.

AI has improved efficiencies in the performance of different administrative tasks that instructors, would require a lot of time to perform in the absence of AI. Other studies have also highlighted the integration of AI into machines or robots and creation of powerful instructional tools and improvement of the quality of the applied pedagogical strategies. Indeed, Timms highlights that another key form of application of AI in education as an instruction tool is the integration of AI in education principles in robots, the development and use of robots as teacher assistants and colleagues, cobots, which can be used to undertake basic and even advanced teaching tasks, such as teaching students to read and pronounce words. Indeed, Sharma et al. observed that the integration or the use of AI in education, more particularly, integration with other technologies and use as instructional tools, has resulted in the development and use of better teaching tools⁶.

From the different articles and studies reviewed, it is evident that with technological innovations and advancements, computers and computer related technologies, and other

⁴ B. Whitby, *Artificial Intelligence: A Beginner's Guide*. Oxford, U.K.: Oneworld, 2018.

⁵ Y. Fang, P. Chen, G. Cai, F. C. M. Lau, S. C. Liew, and G. Han, "Outage-limit-approaching channel coding for future wireless communications: Root-protograph low-density parity-check codes," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 85–93, Jun. 2019.

⁶ S. Pokrivcakova, "Preparing teachers for the application of AI-powered technologies in foreign language education," *J. Lang. Cultural Edu.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 135–153, Dec. 2019.

innovations have encouraged the development of artificial intelligence, which has permeated different sectors of the society, and will potentially have a major impact on different industries in which it is used. One of these areas in which AI has been applied, and is resulting in a major impact, is the education sector. As a foundation, and basis for understanding how AI has impacted education, a definition and description of AI was deemed essential. AI provides students with practical or experiential learning experiences, particularly when used together with other technologies, such as virtual reality, 3-D, gaming, and simulation, thereby improving the students' learning experiences. One study discussed or highlighted the adverse impact of AI, degradation of academic integrity and cheating using paper churning and paper mill services facilitated by AI. Most of the studies analyzed demonstrated and explained the different ways in which AI, including integration, benefits, and impact on administration, instruction, and learning when used in education. The positive effects, the pros, outweigh the cons, or the negative effects.

Conclusion

The objective or the purpose of this study was to assess the impact of AI on education. A qualitative research study, leveraging literature review as a research design and method was used. Journal articles, professional publications, and professional conference reports were identified and used in an analysis that facilitated the realization of the study purpose. The development and use of computers and computer related technologies harbingered research and innovations that have led to the development and use of AI in different sectors. Particularly, the development of the personal computers, and later developments that have increasing the processing and computing capabilities, as well as the ability to integrate or embed computer technologies in different machines, equipment, and platforms, have encouraged the development and use of AI, which has been shown to have a major impact on the sectors it permeates. AI has been extensively adopted and used in the education sector, particularly, in education institutions, which were the focus of this study. The analysis focused on evaluating the impact of AI on administrative, instruction, and learning aspect of education, with a focus on assessing how AI has been applied and the effects it has had. AI in education initially took the form of computers and computer-related systems, and later, the form of web-based and online education platform. Embedded systems have made it possible to use robots, in the form of cobots or humanoid robots as teacher colleagues or independent instructors, as well as chatbots to perform teacher or instructor-like functions. The use of these platforms and tools have enabled or improved teacher effectiveness and efficiency, resulting in richer or improved instructional quality. Similarly, AI has provided students with improved learning experiences because AI has enabled the customization and personalization of learning materials to the needs and capabilities of students. Overall, AI has had a major impact on education, particularly, on administration, instruction, and learning areas of the education sector or within the context of individual learning institutions.

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